

THE ROLE OF ANGIOGENIC FACTORS AND INDICATORS OF THE HEMOSTASIS SYSTEM IN PREDICTING PREGNANCY COMPLICATIONS AFTER IVF

Ro'ziyeva Dilnoza O'ktamovna

Bukhara state medical institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11526639>

Currently, it has been proven that the formation of pregnancy complications is based on violations of the stages of trophoblast invasion and insufficient transformation of spiral arteries, leading to a decrease in blood supply to the growing placenta, hypoxia, impaired secretion of angiogenic factors, spontaneous miscarriages, intrauterine growth retardation and fetal death, placental abruption and gestosis [1,2]. In the pathogenesis of pregnancy complications such as placental insufficiency, fetal growth retardation syndrome, preeclampsia, an important role is played by an imbalance in the production of growth factors responsible for both the condition of the vascular wall and angiogenesis of the placenta and, accordingly, for its proper formation and development.

Pathological invasion of the trophoblast into the spiral arteries contributes to the development of various pregnancy complications, leads to placental ischemia and gestosis, placental insufficiency and fetal growth retardation syndrome [3-6]. Chorion detachment and fetal loss in early pregnancy account for 20-25% of all pregnancies [1,7,8].

The identification of markers of thrombophilia, key markers of angiogenesis, will allow us to develop modern approaches to the diagnosis of pregnancy complications after IVF at the preclinical stage of their development and to carry out early prevention and therapy.

The aim of the study was to identify the relationship between disorders of hemostasis, angiogenic growth factors and pregnancy complications after IVF.

A prospective study of 53 patients with tubal-peritoneal and male infertility factors entering the ART program was conducted. Depending on the data obtained, they were divided by us into 3 groups. The main group consisted of 18 patients with established thrombophilia, including multifactorial forms. The comparison group consisted of 21 patients without thrombophilia, but with a violation of the hemostasis system in the form of severe hypercoagulation, significantly different from hypercoagulation in physiological pregnancy, the so-called chronic form of DIC syndrome on the background of hormonal stimulation of ovulation. The control group included 14 patients without thrombophilia and hemostasis disorders, but also participating in the IVF program due to the

presence of tubal-peritoneal and male infertility factors. The number of IVF cycles was no more than three. The study did not include patients with other infertility factors other than tubal-peritoneal and male factors, multiple pregnancies, aggravated somatic anamnesis. All pregnant women were comparable in terms of anamnesis, reproductive function and age.

The examination was performed at the time from the beginning of ovulation stimulation to delivery every 4 weeks.

Results and discussion

Given the low rates of pregnancy after the first IVF cycle, additional risk factors for non-pregnancy were identified, which included thrombophilia and hypercoagulation in the hemostasis system.

According to our data, a low percentage of pregnancy was detected in pregnant women with thrombophilia, they underwent anticoagulant therapy by subcutaneous administration of low molecular weight heparin (NMH). As a result of the treatment in the repeated IVF cycle, pregnancy rates increased from 6.7% to 30%. Pregnancy progressed under the control of a hemostasiogram in patients with thrombophilia. The study of the levels of soluble receptor of vascular endothelial growth factor 1 (sRVEGF 1) and placental growth factor (PIGF) showed a significant slow increase in blood plasma during the 1st and 2nd trimester of pregnancy in all groups.

However, the level of soluble vascular endothelial growth factor receptor 1 in the group with thrombophilia is 1.3 times higher than in pregnant women without hemostasis disorders, while the level of placental growth factor is 1.3 times lower than in patients with physiological pregnancy.

The early and late postpartum periods also proceeded without complications. The absence of hemorrhagic complications during delivery is more likely to be associated with timely correction of hemostatic disorders.

Thus, in women after ART, a comprehensive examination is necessary, starting from the first trimester of pregnancy, which, in addition to ultrasound, includes the determination of thrombophilic status and angiogenic growth factors.

A decrease in the level of PIGF indices, an increase in sVEGFR1 values, and a violation of uteroplacental blood flow during Dopplerometry in the first trimester of pregnancy makes it possible to identify risk factors for the development of the threat of termination of pregnancy, PI and gestosis. Timely diagnosis of hemostatic system disorders and determination of the level of angiogenic factors allows for preventive and pathogenetically justified,

differentiated therapy, which will reduce the incidence of pregnancy complications after IVF.

References:

1. Стрижаков А.Н. Потеря беременности / А.Н. Стрижаков, И.В. Игнатко. — М.: «Медицинское информационное агентство», 2007. — 224 с.
2. Тимохина Е.В. Синдром задержки роста плода: патогенез, прогнозирование, акушерская тактика: автореферат дис. ... доктора медицинских наук: 14.01.01 / Москва, 2012. - 48 с.
3. Kumazaki, K. Expression of vascular endothelial growth factor, placental growth factor, and their receptors Flt-1 and KDR in human placenta under pathologic conditions / K. Kumazaki [et al.] //Hum. Pathol. -2002. -Vol. 33; No11.-p. 1069-1077.
4. Bartha, J.L. Fluman chorionic gonadotropin and vascular endothelial growth factor in normal and complicated pregnancies [Text]/ J.L. Bartha [et al.] //Obstet. Gynecol. - 2003. - Vol.5. - p.995-999.
5. Espinoza, J. Unexplained fetal death: another anti-angiogenic state / J. Espinoza [et al.] // J. Matern. Fetal. Neonatal. Med. - 2007. - Vol. 20; No 7. - p. 495 - 507.
6. Wallner, W . Angiogenic growth factors in maternal and fetal serum in pregnancies complicated by intrauterine growth restriction / W. Wallner [et al.] //Clin. Sci. (Lond). -2007.- vol.112; No1.- p.51-57.
7. Фадеева Н.И. Кравцова Е.С.Лечение пациенток с угрозой прерывания беременности и профилактика первичной плацентарной недостаточности при частичной отслойке хориона в эмбриональной стадии развития плодного яйца // Российский вестник акушера-гинеколога <http://www.mediasphera.ru/journals/akuvest/detail/83/765/>
8. Кирющенко П.А., Белоусов Д.М., Александрина О.С. Патогенетическое обоснование тактики ведения отслойки хориона и плаценты на ранних сроках беременности // Гинекология. – 2010. – Т. 12, № 1. – С. 36–39.

